

Correlates of Managerial Practices of Principals in Private Elementary Schools in Four Western Towns of Tarlac

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Abstract:- This study was conducted to describe the principals' personal attributes and managerial practices, and the job satisfaction and job performance of teachers in private elementary schools. It also determined the extent of difference between the self-ratings of the principals and the ratings of the teachers in terms of principal's managerial practices and the relationship of principal's managerial practices to their personal attributes and to the job satisfaction and job performance of their teachers. It also described the problems encountered by the teachers in terms of principals' managerial practices.

The respondents of the study were fifteen (15) principals and one hundred five (105) teachers in private elementary schools in four western towns of Tarlac during the school year 2018-2019. Data were gathered, tabulated, and analyzed using the descriptive-comparative-correlational research method. Five sets of questionnaires were used; two for the principals and the other sets were for the teacher respondents.

The significant findings of the study are as follows:

The majority of the principals in private schools are more than 40 years old, with graduate schooling, still new in the position as principal, and attending in-service training related to management at the regional level. The principals rated themselves *effective* in terms of managerial practices. This was in conformity with the ratings of their teachers. Teachers are *very satisfied* with their job in terms of security, work environment, job responsibilities, and community linkages. The performance rating of the teachers given by the academic coordinators/principals is *very satisfactory*. Principals have different perceptions of their managerial practices as compared to their teachers. The managerial practices of the principals are strongly associated with the job satisfaction of the teachers. The managerial practices of the principals are significantly related to their teachers' job performance. The personal attributes of the principals are significantly related to their managerial practices except for age. The top problems encountered by the teachers in terms of their principals' managerial practices along with planning, controlling, and leading are: principals are not giving orientation to the teachers on how to prepare and implement action plans; lack of support in sending teachers to seminars/conferences; and principals seldom or do not supervise the teachers in their teaching/learning assignments. The proposed Principals' Managerial Practices Model for Private Elementary Schools depicts

the positive correlation of managerial practices of principals to their personal attributes and to the job satisfaction and job performance of the teachers.

I. INTRODUCTION

Education has often been considered as the finest instrument in the growth and development of the country. It is considered as the key to a nation's prosperity. It is a long range and complex activity that cannot exist without planning. The educational environment is undergoing relentless change, transformation and reform.

A school organization, like any other organization, needs a strong management and a competent employee. Both set the way the school organization will go. The application of different management practices and the good performances of the teachers in school setting complement each other. Management of school activities are the challenges in the field of education in promoting the culture of lifelong learning and teaching.

In a school organization, the school principal serves as the manager and leader who sets the direction the school is going. The principal is basically responsible in the overall operation of the school. The tremendous changes in scope, variety of competencies, and necessary skills of managing the school make the principal's functions more complex, diverse, and challenging. These functions of school principals as an educational leader and manager are essential to the areas of management namely: the vision, mission, and goals of the institution, curriculum and instruction, financial and budgeting, school plant and facilities, student services, community relations, and the school improvement plan.

The teacher, as one of the most respected profession in the world is the spindle of any education system. In fact, teachers are considered as the strength of a nation. They develop performance style characteristics to their ways of relating to the world, perceptually as well as cognitively. Teacher's positive attitude towards teaching and higher aspiration level determines his positive perception of the environments. For development of quality teachers, one has to understand the factors associated with it. Job satisfaction is one of the important factors. Teachers who are not satisfied with their job will not be committed and productive.

Effective manager and employees' job satisfaction are two factors that have been regarded as fundamental for organizational success. A capable leader provides direction for the organization and lead followers towards achieving desired goals. In similar vein, employees with high job

satisfaction are likely to exert more effort in their assigned tasks and pursue organisational interests. An organization that fosters high employee job satisfaction is also more capable of retaining and attracting employees with the skills that it needs (Mosadegh Rad and Yarmohammadian, 2006).

For these reasons and situations the researcher was motivated to conduct the study to give insights on how personal attributes and managerial practices of principals affect teachers' job satisfaction and performance where principals are expected to know and perform as manager/leader. The researcher also believes that through this study, principals and those aspiring to be one will reflect on the importance of knowing the roles, responsibilities, and functions expected of them in different areas of school management. The results of this study may be useful in identifying the causes of job dissatisfaction among teachers and the causes why some teachers are not performing well and leave the field of education as their career choice.

II. STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

This study aimed to determine the managerial practices of principals in relation to the job satisfaction and job performance of the teachers in private elementary schools in four Western towns in Tarlac during the school year 2018-2019.

Specifically, it sought to answer the following problems:

- How are the principals described along the following personal attributes:
 - age,
 - educational attainment,
 - years of experience as school head, and
 - seminars attended related to leadership or management?
- How are the principals' managerial practices described in terms of:
 - planning,
 - organizing,
 - controlling,
 - leading,
 - supervising,
 - budgeting, and
 - staffing?
- How is the level of job satisfaction of teachers described?
- How is the level of job performance of teachers described?
- To what extent do the self-ratings of principals differ from the ratings of the teachers in terms of their managerial practices?
- To what extent do the managerial practices of principals relate to the job satisfaction of their teachers?
- To what extent do the managerial practices of principals relate to the job performance of their teachers?
- To what extent do the personal attributes of the principal relate to their managerial practices?
- What are the problems encountered by the teachers in relation to the managerial practices of their principals?
- What managerial practices model may be proposed for principals in private elementary schools?

A. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The following are the objectives of the study:

- To describe the personal attributes of principals in terms of their:
 - age,
 - educational attainment,
 - years of experience as school head, and
 - seminars attended related to leadership or management.
- To describe the managerial practices of principals in terms of:
 - planning,
 - organizing,
 - controlling,
 - leading,
 - supervising,
 - budgeting, and
 - staffing.
- To describe the level of job satisfaction of teachers.
- To describe the level of job performance of teachers.
- To determine to the extent of difference between the self – rating of the principals to the rating of the teachers in terms of their managerial practices.
- To determine the extent of relationship between the managerial practices of principals to the job satisfaction of their teachers.
- To determine the extent of relationship between the managerial practices of principals to the job performance of their teachers.
- To determine the extent of relationship of the personal attributes of principals to their managerial practices.
- To determine the problems encountered by the teachers in relation to the managerial practices of their principals.
- To propose a managerial practices model for principals in private elementary schools.

B. Hypotheses of the Study

The following hypotheses were tested at 5% level of significance:

- There is no significant difference between the self-ratings of the principals and the ratings of the teachers in terms of their managerial practices.
- There is no significant relationship between the managerial practices of the principals and the job satisfaction of their teachers.
- There is no significant relationship between the managerial practices of the principals and the job performance of their teachers.
- There is no significant relationship between the personal attributes of the principals and their managerial practices.

C. Significance of the Study

This study could hopefully provide valuable information about the managerial practices of the principals in relation to the job satisfaction and job performance of the teachers in private elementary schools in four western towns in Tarlac.

To the Department of Education (DepEd) Authorities. The study may serve as a key to build upon the available body of knowledge relating to teacher's job

satisfaction and job performance, and the managerial practices among principals. Findings can lead to improvement in the school head preparation program in order to raise their managerial practices.

To the Alliance of Private Schools in Tarlac Province (APSTAP) Authorities. The boards of the APSTAP may use the results of this study in preparing plans and programs for managerial training geared towards improving the competencies of the principals.

To the Principals. Being functional leaders, they face challenges in the process of managing the school. They would be benefited from the findings of this study because they would be fully aware of their functions, duties and responsibilities as instructional leaders and administrative managers of the school. Likewise, this study may present opportunities for self-appraisal of the elementary school heads and sufficient bases for reassessing their strengths and weaknesses.

To the Teachers. They would be benefited from this study because they will be provided with some insights on the managerial practices of their principals. Knowing the factors that contribute to teachers' job performance and satisfaction will enable school heads to provide their teachers a pleasant working conditions to strengthen and sustain the high level of job performance. The findings may serve as basis to improve and promote quality education in the elementary schools.

To the Learners. They would be benefited from this study because they are the direct beneficiaries of whatever improvements in the school system directed towards achieving the quality education.

To the Future Researcher. The study will benefit future researchers for additional information on the field of educational management.

D. Scope and Limitation of the Study

This study was conducted to determine the relationship between the managerial practices of principals and the job satisfaction and job performance of the teachers in private elementary schools in four western towns of Tarlac.

The study covered fifteen (15) complete private elementary schools in four western towns of Tarlac. The respondents involved were the principals and the teachers for the school year 2018-2019.

Survey questionnaires were used to gather the personal attributes and managerial practices of the principals and the job satisfaction and performance of the teachers.

E. Definition of Terms

The following terms were conceptually and operationally defined to make their use and meaning explicitly clear.

- **Age.** This refers to the number of years of the respondent on his last birthday at the time of the study.
- **Budgeting.** It refers to the formulation of plans for a given future period in numerical term.

- **Controlling.** This refers to monitoring activities of the organization to attain objectives.
- **Educational Attainment.** It refers to the highest formal education of a school head such as BEED/BSED and equivalent, BEED/BSED with MA/MS units, MA/MS graduate, MA/MS with doctoral units and Ph./Ed. D graduates.
- **Job Performance.** It most commonly refers to whether a person performs their job well. Despite the confusion over how it should be exactly defined, performance is an extremely important criterion that relates to organizational outcomes and success. In this study, it refers to the Performance Rating of the teachers at the end of the school year.
- **Job Satisfaction.** It is defined as the attitude of an employee toward a job, sometimes expressed as a hedonic response of liking or disliking the work itself, the rewards pay, promotions, recognition, or the context such as working conditions, benefits (Corsini, 1999 as cited by Tillman, 2008).
- **Leading.** It is defined as a function required the use of authority to achieve objectives and goals as well as the ability to communicate effectively.
- **Managerial Practices.** This refers to the working methods and innovations the managers use to improve the effectiveness of work systems.
- **Organizing.** It is defined as a systematic process of structuring, integrating and coordinating task goals and activities in order to attain objectives.
- **Planning.** It refers to the function of management that involves setting objectives and determining a course of action for achieving those objectives.
- **Seminars Attended.** This refers to the in-service training attended by the principal for his/her professional growth.
- **Staffing.** It involves managing and keeping manned the positions provided for the organizational structure. It includes appraising and selecting candidates for the positions, compensating or training candidates and incumbents to accomplish their tasks effectively.
- **Supervising.** It refers to the practices of school heads in monitoring and regulating their subordinates on their responsibilities to improve instruction.
- **Years of Experience.** This refers to the number of years the principal had been managing a school.

III. REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE AND STUDIES

This chapter presents a theoretical knowledge of the managerial practices of principals and its relation to teachers' job satisfaction and performance. The chapter is organized to release strong necessary power of information to conduct the study effectively as well as to develop smart data collection instruments. For the purposes of this study, a wide range of relevant literature and studies were consulted with special reference to those pertaining to managerial practices, theories and factors affecting teachers' job satisfaction and performance which help the researcher to see various findings in different areas.

A. Related Literature

Every supervisor in every organization performs certain roles/tasks for the smooth running of the organization and improvement of organizational performance. As a result, Ezeuwa (2005) sees it as the act of manipulating people so that they strive willingly and enthusiastically towards the accomplishment of goals. In the same manner, Ukeje (1999) observes that leadership means influencing people to work willingly with zeal towards the achievement of the corporate goals. A manager cannot work alone; he must have people to influence, direct, carry along, sensitize and mobilize towards the achievement of the corporate goal. Some managers are more interested in the performance being done than in the people they work with while others pay more attention to their relationship and satisfaction of their employee. Whether a manager emphasizes the task or human relations is usually considered central to their managerial practices.

Aquino (1981) stated that to be an effective school administrator, one must be competent in the performance of the various tasks, functions, activities. He further discussed that there are six categories of major administrative and supervisory tasks and functions which a school administrator must deal with curriculum and instruction, evaluation and supervision, the staff and the students, school community relations, non-formal education and school business administration.

According to Goldman (2002), democratic organizations typically have the following six characteristics: policies are determined by a group of organizations, technical and job performance measures are discussed so they are understood by all, leaders provide advice to members in regards to implementing tasks, members are free to choose with whom they work, the group determines the distribution of tasks, and leaders try to be objective in giving praise and criticism.

According to Koontz (2007), management is a practice of consciously and continually shaping organizations. All organizations have people who are responsible for helping them to achieve their goals. These people are called managers. These managers-coaches, conductors, sales executives – may be more obvious in some organizations than in others, but without effective management, organizations are likely to founder. Management is the principle activity that makes a difference in how well organizations serve people affected by them.

Pareek (2009) stated that measure of how efficient and effective an organization is or how well it achieves appropriate objectives can be defined as organization performance. Organizations are confronted by continuous change to their products, services, processes, markets, competition and technology. These changes require managers to respond with new ways of thinking and behaving. Increasingly, it is recognized that the knowledge and skills of managers affect the competitive advantage of organizations. Numerous researchers have studied the managerial role and the skills required for effective performance.

According to Carver *et al.* (2008), teaching is one of the few vocations that have a lasting impact on society by having a direct influence on future generations. It is one of the greatest professions and one that is ever changing. Over the past 20 years, the teaching profession has undergone many modifications. The teaching profession faces challenges that continuously reconfigure knowledge, rules, skills, attitudes, and ways of professional development (Massari, 2015). Education has changed and developed fundamentally due to social, cultural, and political changes (Saeed *et al.*, 2011).

According to Billingsley *et al.* (2011), the constantly changing field of education is both very demanding and challenging for educators. Teachers need support and guidance to assist them as they learn to be successful educators in the classroom lead followers towards achieving desired goals. An organization that fosters high employee's job satisfaction is more capable of retaining and attracting employees with the skills that it needs.

Forbes (2011) stated in his article, "Trends and Issues: Roles of School Managers as Instructional Leaders, Administrator and Manager" that effective school managers are expected to be academically goal oriented and supervise instructional and co-curricular practices accordingly. They motivate and support the teachers, encourage the community and other school stakeholders to be involved in the educational program, and encourage participatory decision making. They are also faced with the complex task of creating a school wide vision, being an instructional leader-planning for effective professional development, guiding teachers, handling discipline, attending important events and needs, and all the other minute details that come with supervising and managing a school. The job of a school principal, if not more demanding and difficult than an ordinary teacher, is expected to be equal, hence "the quality of school principals as school managers is a factor in improving the quality of education".

According to Kwenin (2013), leaders within organizations can adopt appropriate leadership styles to affect employee job satisfaction, commitment and productivity. Leadership at work in education institutions is thus a dynamic process where an individual is not only responsible for the group's tasks, but also actively seeks the collaboration and commitment of all the group members in achieving group goals in a particular context. Leadership in that context pursues effective performance in schools, because it does not only examine tasks to be accomplished and who executes them, but also seeks to include greater reinforcement characteristics like recognition, conditions of service and morale building, coercion and remuneration.

Ramos (2009) stressed that an administrator's job is to get things in the right place, in the right way and by the right person. He should cultivate good personal appearance, pleasant mannerism, friendliness, cheerfulness and good health so that he can command respect among subordinates. He should process honesty, intelligence, enthusiasm, aggressiveness, loyalty, initiative, industry, perseverance

and decisiveness so as to establish his employee's confidence in him. He should possess adaptability, understanding, patience and self-control so that he will be able to see the true sides of any problem in his office thus exercising fairness to all. Such are the ideal qualities of a good administrators; qualities that serve as ingredients to good public relations which promotes the employee's job satisfaction.

Sternberg (2016) said that there are key capabilities of a 21st Century school leader: the leader's ability to innovate is to be creative, to think outside the box, to collaborate both within the school and external industry bodies and the community to find opportunities for learning beyond the classroom; the leader's ability to inspire others is to rethink, reimagine, relearn, regroup and reschedule aspects of teaching and learning design and overcome risk aversion; and the leader's ability to affect change is to carry out the necessary organizational changes needed to influence culture, climate, system, policy, processes, environment, pedagogy and the network of collective thinking in education.

Namoro (2008), in his article "How to Become An Effective School Administrator", enumerated the following for the development of the staff: school level in-service training is indispensable wherein school managers with the help of the Master Teachers select the best subject matter in the seminar, school managers must understand programs, innovations and requirements of the DepEd and should be aware of all Memoranda, Circulars, Orders, Bulletins and letters coming from the top managers, they should also avoid uttering bad words during conference and should see to it that there is no communication gap between him and his teachers, and democratic leadership should always be applied in administration and supervision.

B. Related Studies

Cruz (2016) conducted a study on "Enhancing the Managerial Performance of School Heads" and he elucidated that successful school managers should be interested in developing and adopting necessary skills to create the best teaching and learning environment. The evolving needs of the school organization grow out of the never-ending pressure from the different stakeholders in the educational system. The capacity to perform both as leaders and managers shapes the school organization as a whole. The call for enhancing the leadership and managerial competencies of school heads as the most influential person in promoting reform, change, and innovations in performing these functions challenges educational leaders. The emerging changes in leading and managing organizations should be dealt with by discovering new opportunities and threats attached to these and at the same time reconciling these with essential management processes. One must understand the changes in school environment, but the application of proven fundamentals of planning, organizing, leading and controlling remain unchanged. They are as relevant as they were years ago but their form continuously evolves.

Larkin *et al.* (2016) stated that teachers who have higher level of job satisfaction also have higher level of performance and are less likely to leave the field of education to pursue other career choices. There are many variables that may be attributed to teachers' level of job satisfaction including workplace conditions, salary, and relationship with staff, students' behaviour, parents' participation, and a supportive administration.

Salfi (2011) revealed in her study on "Successful Leadership Practices of Head Teachers for School Improvement", that the majority of the head teachers of successful schools developed a common and shared school vision and promoted a culture of collaboration, support and trust. They empowered others to lead and distributed leadership responsibilities throughout the school; involved different stakeholders in the process of decision making; developed and maintained good relationships among different personnel of school community. They emphasized the professional development of teachers as well as themselves, and involved parents and community in the process of school improvement.

Pobre (2009) revealed in her study on "Administrative and Supervisory Competencies of Public Elementary School Managers", that the highest degree earned, advanced units, education in educational management in service training, seminars, attended, numbers of years as school managers and performance rating do not influence the supervisory competencies of school managers. The selected variables are "weak" predictors of supervisory competencies.

Mazibuko (2007) in his study "The Managerial Role of The Principal in Whole-School Evaluation in the Context of Disadvantaged Schools" revealed that changes taking place in the education system have influence on the roles performed by different individuals in the school environment. For example, principals have to ensure that whole-school evaluation is effectively implemented at school. To do that effectively means that the principal needs to acquire new skills of performing his/her roles. The research also reveals that because of changes taking place in the education system principals have to regularly attend meetings, workshops and departmental briefings. As a result they do not have enough time to attend to their duties in their schools. The study also found that because of information overload, principals are sometimes unable to provide guidance, direction and support to their staff members.

Dacara (2002) stated in her study that personality traits of school heads can influence their management practices and the physical traits have significant relationship with all management practices except information dissemination. Intellectual traits were significantly related to all management practices.

Estrada (2013) stated that management is a purposive activity. It is something that directs group efforts towards the attainment of certain pre-determined goals. It is the process of working with and through others to effectively achieve the goals of the organization, by efficiently using

limited sources in the changing world. Of course, these goals may vary from one enterprise to another. It is the management which puts into use the various factors of production. Therefore, it is the responsibility of the management to create such conditions which are conducive to maximum efforts so that people are able to perform their task efficiently and effectively. It includes ensuring availability of raw materials, determination of wages and salaries, formulation of rules and regulation and others.

Joves (2013) stated in her study “Correlates of Leadership Style of Public Secondary School Heads in Cluster I, Division of Tarlac” that many managers choose to rely on intuition. They depend upon bright ideas, their personal ability or that of their subordinates for the successful accomplishment of their jobs. Now managing by intuition may result in an adequate organization but it seldom results in a complete sound one. She also revealed that to be an effective school manager, one must be competent in the performance of the various tasks, functions and activities.

Dela Cruz (2012) revealed that leadership has significant impacts on job satisfaction and organizational commitment of an employee. High job satisfaction enhances employees’ psychological and physical wellbeing and positively affects employee performance. He pointed out that job satisfaction is influenced by many organizational contextual factors, ranging from salaries, job autonomy, job security, workplace flexibility, to leadership.

Andal (2015) focused his study on the level of job satisfaction and performance of the faculty. He found out that his respondents are performing their job well because intrinsic and extrinsic rewards are given to deserving faculty. These rewards may be in the form of recognition and citations, better working conditions; scholarship; travel grants and others. The respondents are always hungry for new learning and innovations that would satisfy their curiosity.

Macalma (2016) stated that good performance of employees arises when supervisors are understanding and very friendly, listens to employees opinions, show personal interest in them and subsequently praises the employees for their good performance. Therefore, the interpersonal relationship and quality supervision must be properly observed in the organization.

Nuyles (2011) revealed that teacher’s competence and effectiveness of teaching performance are indicated by the achievement of pupils. Learning is an outcome of effective teaching performance which is a concrete manifestation of

teacher’s teaching performance. Thus, it seems logical to conclude that measures of teaching performance may predict effective teaching performance and pupil achievement.

C. Theoretical/Conceptual Framework

This study was guided by two theories: the Expectancy Theory of Motivation by Vroom (1964) and the Two-Factor Theory by Frederick Herzberg. Expectancy Theory is a goal-setting model in which he believed that performance is determined by the product of motivation and ability. It suggests that an individual engages in behaviour where he expects to lead him to positive outcomes and rewards that are well-motivated would ensure higher level of job satisfaction. A teacher who is satisfied with his job performs better than those who are less motivated.

The study was also anchored on Herzberg’s Two-Factor. Herzberg stated that people have different categories of needs that were essentially independent of each other and which affect them in different ways. He classified these into two factors known as Motivator and Hygiene. Motivator was found to be important in motivating employees to superior performance and in improving productivity. It is indicated that when an employee’s felt good about their jobs they were motivated to work because they found the job challenging and satisfying with the expectations of accomplishment and reward. On the other hand, the presence of Hygiene is to maintain the current levels of efficiency and production but not to improve the production or job performance. Said condition concern the environment in which they were working such as company, policy supervision, salary interpersonal relations and working conditions. Thus, if the hygiene factors are inadequate, the workers will feel dissatisfied.

School managers, as expected should manifest satisfactory performance along the following aspects: planning, organizing, controlling, leading, supervising, budgeting, and staffing to motivate employees in doing their duties and responsibilities.

Based on the paradigm of this study, it is conceptualized that the personal attributes of the principals affect their managerial practices. If principals’ managerial performance is high, the level of job satisfaction among teachers will become higher too. Teachers who gained higher level of satisfaction with their job will have the tendency to be more effective and efficient in doing their tasks as a classroom manager. Figure 1 presents the conceptual paradigm showing the relationship of the variables under study.

IV. METHODS AND PROCEDURE

This chapter presents the methods and the procedure that this study utilized in collecting, collating, analysing, and interpreting the data that provided answers to the problems raised. It comprises the research design, respondents of the study, data gathering procedure, data gathering instrument and the data analysis scheme.

A. Research Design

The descriptive-comparative-correlational research method was used in this study. The study mainly described the personal attributes and managerial practices of school principals, and the job performance and job satisfaction of teachers based on the constructed questionnaires answered by the respondents. It is comparative because it determined the difference between the self-ratings of principals and ratings of teachers in terms of principals' managerial practices. It is also correlational since it determined the

relationship of principal's personal attributes to their managerial practices and the relationship of principal's managerial practices to the job performance and job satisfaction of the teachers.

B. Location of the Study

The study was conducted in 15 complete private elementary schools in four western towns of Tarlac during the school year 2018 – 2019.

C. Respondents of the Study

The respondents of the study were the 15 school heads and 105 teachers from 15 private elementary schools in four western towns of Tarlac.

Table 1 shows the names of school and the number of principals and teachers from each private school in four western towns of Tarlac.

TOWN	SCHOOL	NO. OF PRINCIPAL	NO. OF TEACHERS
Sta. Ignacia	Santa Ignacia Catholic School of Tarlac	1	7
	Santa Ignacia Baptist Church Christian Academy	1	7
	Glory Dei Montessori School	1	7
	Accelerated Learning Academy	1	7
Mayantoc	Glory Dei Montessori School	1	7
	Mayantoc Academy, Inc.	1	7
Camiling	Meri Life Learning Academy, Inc.	1	7
	Bestcap Career College	1	7
	Camiling Catholic School	1	7
	Asian Lexcon School	1	7
	Camiling Colleges	1	7
	Seventh Day Adventist School	1	7
	Bright Kid School	1	7
San Clemente	Immanuel Montessori	1	7
	Christian Academy	1	7
Total		15	105

Table 1: Number of school heads and teachers in private elementary schools in four western towns of Tarlac

D. Data Gathering Instrument

The researcher used five sets of questionnaires. Set I questionnaire was used to gather data on the principals' profile answered by the principal respondents. Set II questionnaire was adapted from Gabatino (2003) was cast-off to gather data on the managerial performance of school heads through self-rating and rating by their teachers. Set III questionnaire, adapted from Glorineil D. Romero (2017) and set IV questionnaire adopted from DepEd, were used to elicit responses for the job satisfaction and together information of the performance appraisal of teachers and the last set of questionnaire was cast-off supported by interview by the researcher to elicit information on the problems encountered by the teachers on the managerial practices of their principals.

E. Data Gathering Procedure

Permission, assistance and support were asked from the school principals of the different private elementary schools in four western towns of Tarlac to conduct the survey among teachers in their respective schools.

The questionnaires were distributed personally to the principals and teachers of the different private elementary schools.

After a week, the survey questionnaires were retrieved and the data were collated, tallied, and classified/organized in preparation for the application of the statistical treatments. Validation of the data gathered was conducted by the researcher through random interview with some teachers and principals.

F. Units of Analysis

The units of analysis of the study were the school principals and teachers of different private elementary schools in four western town of Tarlac.

G. Data Analysis

For Objective No. 1. To describe the personal attributes of the school principals, frequency and percentage were used.

For Objective No. 2. To describe the managerial practices of principals, weighted mean per category was used.

The items in the questionnaire were scored based on the assigned weight as shown below:

Descriptions	Index
Very Effective	5
Effective	4
Moderately Effective	3
Less Effective	2
Least Effective	1

The frequencies per item were multiplied by the assigned index to get the weighted mean. Below is the conversion of the weighted mean with the corresponding ranges into qualitative descriptions.

Weighted Mean	Qualitative Description
4.50 – 5.00	Very Effective
3.50 – 4.49	Effective
2.50 – 3.49	Moderately Effective
1.50 – 2.49	Less Effective
1.00 – 1.49	Least Effective

For Objective No. 3.To describe the teacher’s job satisfaction, weighted mean was used.

Descriptions	Index
Highly Satisfied	5
Very Satisfied	4
Satisfied	3
Less Satisfied	2
Least Satisfied	1

The frequencies per item were multiplied by the assigned index to get the weighted mean. Below is the conversion of the weighted means with the corresponding ranges into qualitative descriptions.

Weighted Mean	Qualitative Description
4.50 – 5.00	Highly Satisfied
3.50 – 4.49	Very Satisfied
2.50 – 3.49	Satisfied
1.50 – 2.49	Less Satisfied
1.00 – 1.49	Least Satisfied

For Objective No. 4.To describe the teacher’s job performance, weighted mean was used.

The items in the questionnaire were scored based on the assigned weight as shown below:

Qualitative Description	Code
Outstanding	5
Very Satisfactory	4
Satisfactory	3
Unsatisfactory	2
Poor	1

The frequencies per item were multiplied by the assigned index to get the weighted mean. Below is the conversion of the weighted means with the corresponding ranges into qualitative descriptions.

Weighted Mean	Qualitative Description
4.50 – 5.00	Outstanding
3.50 – 4.49	Very Satisfactory
2.50 – 3.49	Satisfactory
1.50 – 2.49	Unsatisfactory
1.00 – 1.49	Poor

For Objective No. 5.To determine the extent of difference between the ratings of the principals and the rating of the teachers in terms of their managerial practices, weighted mean was used.

For Objective No. 6.To determine the extent of relationship between the managerial practices of the principals and the job satisfaction of their teachers, multiple linear correlation was used.

For Objective No. 7.To determine the extent of relationship between the managerial practices of the principals and the job performance of their teachers, multiple linear correlation was used.

For Objective No. 8.To determine the extent of relationship of the personal attributes of the principals to their managerial practices, multiple linear correlation was used.

For Objective No. 9.To determine the problems encountered by the teachers in relation to the managerial

practices of their principals, frequency counts was used.

V. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

This portion presents the analysis of data, interpretation of results and discussion of the following: 1) description of personal attributes of the principals such as age, educational attainment, years of experience and seminars/in-service training attended in relation to leadership or management; 2) description of principal’s managerial practices based on self-rating and ratings by their teachers; 3) description of job satisfaction and job performance of the teachers; 4) differences between the self-ratings of the principals and the rating of the teachers in terms of principal’s managerial practices; 5) relationship of personal attributes of the principals to their managerial practices; 6) relationship of principal’s managerial practices to the job satisfaction and job performance of their teachers; and 7) the problems encountered by the teachers in terms of principal’s managerial performance.

A. *Principals' Personal Attributes in Private Elementary School in Four Western Towns of Tarlac*

Table 2 presents the personal attributes of principals in private elementary school in four western towns of Tarlac in

terms of their age, educational attainment, number of years as principal, and seminars/in-service training attended related to leadership and management.

SCHOOL HEADS' PROFILE	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
Age		
29 years old and below	1	6.67
30-39 years old	3	20.00
40-49 years old	5	33.33
50-59 years old	3	20.00
60 years and older	3	20.00
Total	15	100
Educational Attainment		
BEEd/BSE Graduate	3	20.00
BEEd/BSE with Masteral Units	3	20.00
Masteral Graduate	5	33.33
MA with PhD/EdD Units	3	20.00
Ed.D/Ph.D Graduate	1	6.67
Total	15	100
Years as School Head		
5 years and below	8	53.33
6-10 years	2	13.33
11-15 years	1	6.67
16-20 years	4	26.67
Total	15	100
In-service Training Attended*		
National Level	10	66.66
Regional Level	11	73.33
Provincial Level	2	13.33

Table 2. Profile of School Heads of the Four Western Towns of Tarlac

*Multiple response

a) Age

As presented in the table, one or 6.67% of the school heads are 29 years old and below, three or 20% are 30-39 years old, five or 33.33 % are 40-49 year old, three or 20% are 50-59 years old, and three or 20% are 60 years old and above.

The results show that most of the principals are in the middle age. As cited in the study of Antonio (2013), positive shifts occur in the middle years, particularly between 40 and 49. This means that at this age, it is expected that principals are already prepared and competent to perform their administrative and supervisory functions at their best.

b) Educational Attainment

The highest level of schooling that an individual has reached is referred to as educational attainment. As revealed in the data, three or 20% are BEEd/BSE graduates, three or 20% are BEEd/BSE graduates with master's units, five or 33.33% are master's graduates, three or 20% are MA graduates with PhD/EdD units and only one or 6.67% is a PhD/Ed.D graduate.

The data shows that most of the principals are already master's graduate. This may be because

principals know that they have to equip themselves with knowledge and skills needed to perform their managerial taskswell and this can be done by attending graduate studies.

c) Number of Years as Principal

Considering the number of years as principal, the result of the data shows that eight or 53.33% of the respondents have been principal for five years or less; two or 13.33% have been principals for 6-10 years; one or 6.67% for 11-15 years; and four or 26.67% have been serving as principal for 16-20 years.

Result shows that majority of the principals are still new in the service. This is attributed to the fact that private schools are becoming the training grounds of fresh graduate education students. Most of the teachers resign after they accumulate number of years of teaching and transferred in public schools. Another factor is that many of the private schools are newly opened and principals are appointed based on the discretion of the school board or the Bishop who serves as the Director for catholic schools.

d) In-service Training Attended

In-service training refers to the personal growth and professional development of principals that are not enhanced by going through graduate studies. These may update principals on the trends and innovations in education (Altun 2011).

As to the seminars/in service-trainings attended related to leadership and management, it shows that 10 or 66.66% have attended seminars at national level, 11 or 73.33% have attended seminars at the

regional level, and two or 13.33% attended at the provincial level.

Majority of the school heads have attended seminars/in-service trainings in regional and national level. Some of the seminars attended by the principals were on: Understanding and Designing Standards-Based School Improvement, PEAC Executive Course for Educational Management and Curriculum Management Seminar which were usually conducted by the APSTAP, TDSA and PEAC Organization.

B. Managerial Practices of the Principal as Rated by Themselves and Their Teachers

Table 3 presents the managerial practices of the principal as rated by themselves and their teachers.

MANAGERIAL PRACTICES	PRINCIPALS' RATING		TEACHERS' RATING		AVERAGE RATING	
	WM	VD	WM	VD	WM	VD
Planning	4.54	VE	4.14	E	4.34	E
Organizing	4.53	VE	3.98	E	4.25	E
Controlling	4.57	VE	4.02	E	4.295	E
Leading	4.55	VE	3.81	E	4.18	E
Supervising	4.52	VE	4.01	E	4.27	E
Budgeting	4.51	VE	4.13	E	4.32	E
Staffing	4.55	VE	3.87	E	4.21	E
OVERALL	4.54	VE	3.99	E	4.27	E

Table 3: Managerial Practices of the Principal as Rated by Themselves and Their Teachers

Legend:

Weighted Mean (WM)	Verbal Description (VD)
4.50-5.00	Very Effective (VE)
3.50-4.49	Effective (E)
2.50-3.49	Moderate Effective (ME)
1.50-2.49	Less Effective (Ls E)
1.00-1.49	Least Effective (Lt E)

Results show that the principals rated themselves as **very effective** in all the managerial practices like planning, organizing, controlling, leading, supervising, staffing, and budgeting. However, the teachers rated the managerial practices of their principals as **effective** only. The average ratings of the principals and teachers show that the principals are **effective** in their managerial practices.

These results mean that the teachers believed that their principals are doing well in their roles and functions based on all the managerial practices considered in the study.

Planning is the basic process to select goals and determine how to achieve them. It is the process of establishing objective and suitable source of action. (Stoner, 1989). The study revealed that principals rated themselves as **very effective** in planning with a weighted mean at 4.54 while their teachers rated them **effective** with a weighted mean at 4.34. These ratings indicate that principals are effective in setting up goals and priorities for the benefits of the school, learners and teachers.

Organizing is a systematic process of structuring, integrating, coordinating task goals, and activities to resources in order to attain objectives. This task is developed

during the planning stage so that plan can be implemented (Korkmaz, 2007). The study shows that principals rated themselves **very effective** along the aspect of organizing with a weighted mean at 4.53 while the teachers rated them **effective** with a weighted mean at 3.98. Principals carry out school activities and give assignments to teachers related to their capabilities in areas of their concern. It corroborates the study of Velicaria (2013) that administrator had higher expectations of themselves than their teachers.

Controlling is the process of monitoring work performance, comparing results to goals and taking corrective actions as needed (Schemerborn, 1993). As can be gleaned from Table 3, the principals rated themselves **very effective** with a weighted mean at 4.57 and the teachers rated them **effective** with a weighted mean at 4.02. This indicates that the principals have high sense of achievement in their managerial practices while teachers were quite satisfied. The findings revealed that principals are effective in setting up schedule and timetables in accomplishing projects, in monitoring and evaluating objectively and in maintaining definite standard of performance.

Leading is defined as a function which requires the use of authority to achieve objectives and goals as well as

the ability to communicate effectively. Principals ought to have skills in providing direction to teachers toward the improvement of the teaching – learning activities (Chavez, 2002). The data revealed that principals rated themselves *very effective* with a weighted mean of 4.55 while teachers rated them *effective* with a weighted mean of 3.81.

Supervising include activities that are essential in teaching-learning situation that improved instruction. It will provide conditions to improve teaching and learning process (Abwalla,2014). The data reveals that the principals rated themselves *very effective* with a weighted mean of 4.52 while their teachers rated them *effective* with a weighted mean of 4.01. These ratings indicate that principals have good supervising practices and showed positive understanding and good relationship between them and their teachers. As stated in the study of Valecaria (2013), principals demonstrated consideration by paying close attention to differences and uniqueness of teachers and showed respect to their worth.

Budgeting is the operational activity of a business that is responsible for obtaining and effectively utilizing the fund necessary for efficient operations. This is the heart of the administrative process (Zulueta, 1999). The data reveals that principals rated themselves *very effective* with a weighted mean at 4.51 while the teachers rated them *effective* with a weighted mean at 4.13.

Staffing. According to Stoner (1987), the most critical tasks of a principal are the selection, training and development of people. These are the people who supply the

organization with work, talent, creativity and drive. The table shows that the principals rated themselves *very effective* in terms of staffing with a weighted mean at 4.55 while their teachers rated them *effective* with a weighted mean at 3.81. The study revealed that principals are effective in hiring teachers according to needs and qualifications, giving recognition to a job well-done and in providing in-service training for their teachers. As stated in the study of Salfi (2011), majority of the principals empowered others to lead and distribute leadership responsibilities throughout the school; developed and maintained good relationships among different personnel of school community; and emphasized the professional growth and development of teachers as well as of themselves for school improvement and to achieve quality education.

C. Description on Teacher’s Level of Job Satisfaction

Table 4 shows the level of job satisfaction of teachers along security, work environment, job responsibilities and community linkages.

Maslow’s Theory postulates that there are essential needs that have to be met first before more complex needs can be met. This theory supports the study of Herberg (1964) that an individual could perform well if he/she is satisfied with the factors that will motivate an individual. According to Estrada (2013), although job satisfaction is under the influence of many external factors, it remains something internal that has to do with the way how the employee feels. Job satisfaction presents a set of factors that cause a feeling of satisfaction.

JOB SATISFACTION	WEIGHTED MEANS	VERBAL DESCRIPTION
Security	3.28	Satisfied
Work Environment	3.75	Very Satisfied
Job Responsibilities	3.80	Very Satisfied
Community Linkages	3.63	Very Satisfied
Overall	3.62	Very Satisfied

Table 4: Job Satisfaction of Teachers in Private Schools in Four Western Towns of Tarlac for the Last Three Years

Legend:

Weighted Mean (WM)	Verbal Description (VD)
4.50-5.00	Highly Satisfied (HS)
3.50-4.49	Very Satisfied (VS)
2.50-3.49	Satisfied (S)
1.50-2.49	Less Satisfied (LsS)
1.00-1.49	Least Satisfied (LtS)

a) Security

In terms of security that includes salary, benefits, rewards, performance, recognition and promotion, a mean rating of 3.28 was obtained which is described as *satisfied*. This means that teachers are satisfied with the amount of pay or benefits they receive for the work they do. They are also recognized and rewarded for their efforts the way they should be and they have also the chance to be reclassified or promoted.

Zebet *al.* (2015) explains in his study that reward and recognition develop an enthusiasm among employees, increase their desire for work and also establish linkage between performance and motivation of the employees.

According to Nooriet *al.* (2015), job promotion is very important in all sectors around the workplace. This may lead employees to aim for innovation, improved techniques and develop something new for their career. It may also involve discovering new

working atmosphere, improvement, progress, development and advancement of knowledge, learning etc. of the employee.

b) Work Environment

Work environment obtained a mean rating of 3.75 which means that teachers are **very satisfied** with the policies, organizational structures, physical and social environment in the organization because of the good relationship between the principal, teachers, and other members of the school.

Obieta (2010) stated that peers influence the job satisfaction. This is because they are capable of performing their teaching job and they develop the feeling of self-confidence in a positive environment.

c) Job Responsibilities

Job Responsibilities obtained a mean of 3.80 which is described as **very satisfactory**. Teachers are motivated to do their job when they earn the trust of their principal in performing their responsibilities in their own style and when the principal provides them with more challenging works. This is supported by the findings of Douglas McGregor (2001) that when a manager develops a participative style, he/she ensures commitment in the organization. Thus, effort in work is as natural as work and play, people will apply self-control and self-direction in pursuing of organizational objectives without external control or the threat of punishment, commitment to objectives is a function of rewards associated with their achievement, and people usually accept and often seek responsibility. (<http://www.businessballs.com/mcgregor.htm>).

d) Community Linkage

Community linkage obtained a mean rating of 3.63 which means that teachers are **very satisfied**. This indicates that when teachers have the chance to help people in the community, the school has sufficient facilities and the distance of the school from the house is accessible, teachers are very satisfied in their teaching profession. Esparado (2009) stated that people work better when the environment, working methods, and equipment have been designed to help

them. If we add to this the natural motivation to do good job of work for an appropriate reward, we can confidently anticipate improve productivity.

D. Description on Teacher's Level of Job Performance

Teacher's job performance refers to the result of teacher's effort as regard instructional competence such as lesson planning and delivery, learner's achievement, and school, home and community involvement; professional and personal characteristics and punctuality and attendance as evaluated and rated by their principals or academic coordinator objectively.

Table 5 shows the level of job performance of teachers along instructional competence, professional and personal characteristics and punctuality and attendance.

a) Instructional Competence

Instructional competence of the teachers registered a weighted mean of 4.12 showing that teachers have very satisfactory performance in presenting and delivering their lessons, improving learners' achievement, ensuring pupils' participation during discussion and encouraging parents' involvement in school programs and activities. This means that teachers are efficient as classroom managers and they accomplish their functions and duties according to the requirements of the school.

Kunter (2013) defined teacher quality as all teacher-related characteristics that produce favourable educational outcomes such as student performance on standardized test. Article II Sec 4 of the Code of Ethics for Professional Teachers states that "every teacher shall possess and actualize a full commitment and devotion to duty." and article III Sec. 6 stipulates that "every teacher is an intellectual leader in the community, especially in the barangay, and shall welcome the opportunity to provide such leadership when needed, to extend counselling services, as appropriate, and actively be involved in matters affecting the welfare of the people." Therefore, teachers should either maintain or improve his or her intellectual capabilities to cope up with the changes in the community.

PERFORMANCE	WEIGHTED MEANS	VERBAL DESCRIPTION
Instructional Competence	4.12	Very Satisfactory
Professional & Personal Characteristics	4.27	Very Satisfactory
Punctuality of Attendance	4.14	Very Satisfactory
Overall	4.17	Very Satisfactory

Table 5: Job Performance of Teachers in Private Schools in Four Western Towns of Tarlac for the Last Three Years

Legend:

Weighted Mean (WM)	Verbal Description (VD)
4.50-5.00	Outstanding (O)
3.50-4.49	Very Satisfactory (VS)
2.50-3.49	Satisfactory (S)
1.50-2.49	Unsatisfactory (US)
1.00-1.49	Poor (P)

- b) Professional and Personal Characteristics
 The professional and personal characteristics of the teachers registered a weighted mean of 4.27 which is verbally described as *very satisfactory*. This means that teachers manifested the specified personal/professional characteristics like honesty, courtesy, human relations, stress tolerance, commitment, resourcefulness, fairness decisiveness and leadership as enumerated in the Performance Appraisal System for Teachers (PAST). The preamble of Teacher’s Code of Ethics states that “teachers are duly licensed professional who possesses dignity and reputation with high moral values as well as technical and professional competence in the practice of their noble profession, they strictly adhere to, observe and practice this set of ethical and moral principles, standards and values”.
- c) Punctuality and Attendance
 With regards to punctuality and attendance, a weighted mean of 4.14 was obtained which is verbally described as *very satisfactory*. This means that teachers observed punctuality and regular

attendance. They come to school on time and avoid absenteeism.

E. Differences in the Managerial Practices of the Principals as Rated by Themselves and Their Teachers

Table 6 shows the differences in the managerial practices of the principals as rated by themselves and their teachers. Difference in the ratings between the teachers and principals are significant at 5% level if the computed probability is less than .05 and highly significant if the probability is less than .01.

Results indicate that there are high significant differences in the ratings of the principals and their teachers in terms of managerial practices since the probability values are less than .01. These results imply that the perception of the teachers on the managerial practices of their principals like planning, organizing, controlling, leading, supervising, budgeting and staffing do not conform to the self-evaluation of their principals. This further implies that the principals’ perception on their managerial practices is different from their teachers’ perceptions which were based on their observations which may be influenced by value system and their experiences. This result corroborates the study of Velicaria (2013) that administrators had higher expectations of themselves than their teachers.

MANAGERIAL PRACTICES	PRINCIPALS’ MEAN RATING	TEACHERS’ MEAN RATING	PROB.	DIFFERENCE
Planning	4.54	4.14	.0002	Highly Significant
Organizing	4.53	3.98	.0002	Highly Significant
Controlling	4.57	4.02	.0088	Highly Significant
Leading	4.55	3.81	.0000	Highly Significant
Supervising	4.52	4.01	.0000	Highly Significant
Budgeting	4.51	4.13	.0000	Highly Significant
Staffing	4.55	3.87	.0070	Highly Significant

Table 6: Difference in the Managerial Practices of the Principals as Rated by themselves and their Teachers

F. Relationship Between the Managerial Practices of Principal and the Job Performance of Their Teachers

Table 7 shows the relationship between the managerial practices of the principals and the job performance of their teachers. Results revealed that the principals’ managerial practices on planning, organizing, controlling, leading, supervising, and staffing have high significant relationship to the job performance of their teachers since their probability values are less than .01. The positive sign of the

coefficient of correlation means that the more effective the principal is in setting goals and objectives of the school, forming class and teaching schedules and delegating responsibilities, accomplishing projects and monitoring or evaluating teacher’s performance objectively, his or her teachers tend to perform better as well. Analysis further revealed that the effectiveness of principal in budgeting has no significant relationship to the level of job performance of his or her teachers.

MANAGERIAL PRACTICES	COEF. OF CORRELATION	PROB.	RELATIONSHIP
Planning	+.712	.000	Highly Significant
Organizing	+.492	.000	Highly Significant
Controlling	+.611	.000	Highly Significant
Leading	+.559	.000	Highly Significant
Supervising	+.353	.000	Highly Significant
Staffing	+.302	.002	Highly Significant
Budgeting	+.098	.319	Not Significant

Table 7: Relationship Between the Managerial Practices of Principal to the Job Performance of Their Teachers

Macalma (2016) stated that good performance of employees arises when supervisors are understanding and very friendly, listens to employees opinions, and subsequently praises employees for good performance. Therefore, the interpersonal relationship and quality supervision must be properly observed in the organization.

G. Relationship Between the Principals’ Managerial Practices and the Teachers’ Job Satisfaction

Determining the relationship between the managerial practices of the principals and the job satisfaction of the teachers is one of the objectives of the study which is shown in Table 8. It is hypothesized that there is no significant relationship between the managerial practices of principals and the job satisfaction of their teachers.

Analysis revealed that the managerial practices of principals on planning, organizing, controlling, leading,

supervising, and staffing are correlates of teachers’ job satisfaction. These results imply that as the principal becomes more effective doing his or her functions in setting goals and objectives of the school, forming class and teaching schedules and delegating responsibilities, accomplishing projects and monitoring or evaluating teacher’s performance objectively, the level of job satisfaction of the teachers will be high as well. This result conforms the study of Katdonget *al.* (2013) that teachers find job satisfaction when managers’ involvement in school activities is visible. In contrast, budgeting practice of the principal has no significant relationship to job satisfaction of the teachers. This result shows that whether or not the principal is good in budgeting or managing financial resources of the school, it has nothing to do with the job satisfaction of their teachers.

MANAGERIAL PRACTICES	COEF. OF CORRELATION	PROB.	RELATIONSHIP
Planning	+.556	.000	Highly Significant
Organizing	+.228	.019	Significant
Controlling	+.275	.005	Highly Significant
Leading	+.266	.006	Highly Significant
Supervising	+.240	.014	Significant
Staffing	+.655	.000	Highly Significant
Budgeting	+.154	.116	Not Significant

Table 8: Relationship Between the Managerial Practices of Principal and the Job Satisfaction of Their Teachers

Dela Cruz (2012) revealed that leadership and management have significant impacts on job satisfaction and organizational commitment of an employee. High job satisfaction enhances employees’ psychological and physical well-being and positively affects employee performance. He pointed out that job satisfaction is influenced by many organizational contextual factors, ranging from salaries, job autonomy, job security, workplace flexibility, to leadership.

H. Relationship between the Principals’ Attributes and their Managerial Practices

The researcher conceptualized that the personal attributes of the principals such as age, educational attainment, years of experience as principal and in-service trainings attended are correlates of the effectiveness of their managerial practices.

Table 9 presents the relationship between the personal attributes of the principals and their managerial practices.

a) Age

The age of the principals has high significant relationship to their managerial practices on controlling and leading. The positive sign of the coefficient of correlation means that as a principal becomes older he or she becomes better in controlling and leading such as in monitoring activities and using authorities to attain/achieve the objectives and goals of the organization as well as inspiring and encouraging subordinates to do better in pursuing organizational interest through motivation, provisions of incentives and recognition. However, the age of the principals has no significant relationship to their managerial practices in the aspect of planning, organizing, supervising, budgeting and staffing.

PRINCIPALS’ PROFILE	PRINCIPALS’ MANAGERIAL PRACTICES						
	Planning	Organizing	Controlling	Leading	Supervising	Staffing	Budgeting
Age	+.054ns	+.166ns	+.325**	+.280**	+.091ns	+.151ns	+.177ns
Educational Attainment	+.484**	+.307**	+.290**	+.239**	+.497**	+.485**	+.358**
No. of Years as Principal	+.342**	+.657**	+.490**	+.497**	+.714**	+.312**	+.144ns
In-Service Training Attended	+.216**	+.275**	+.165ns	+.228*	+.558**	+.355**	+.092ns

Table 9: Relationship between the Profile of Principals to Their Managerial Practices

Legend:

ns – not significant

* - significant

** - highly significant

b) Educational Attainment

The educational attainment of the principals has high significant relationship to all aspects of their managerial practices. The positive sign of the coefficient of correlation shows that the higher the educational attainment of the principal is, the better the application of his or her managerial practices. These results mean that the principal has the tendency to be very effective in planning, organizing, controlling, leading, supervising, budgeting, and staffing when his or her educational attainment becomes higher.

These results conform to the study conducted by Cruz (2016) on “Enhancing the Managerial Performance of School Heads”. He elucidated that successful school managers should be interested in developing and adopting necessary skills through non-stop learning to create the best teaching and learning environment. As the most influential person in promoting reform, change, and innovations in performing such functions, school heads are challenge to enhance their leadership and managerial competencies. The emerging changes in leading and managing organizations should be dealt with by discovering new opportunities and at the same time reconciling these with essential management processes.

c) Number of Years as Principal

The number of years as principal registered a high significant relationship to all aspects of his or her managerial practices except in budgeting. This result shows that the longer the exposure of principals to their roles and functions as school heads, the better or more effective they could be in performing their managerial practices on planning, organizing, controlling, leading, supervising, and staffing. This result conforms with the findings of Obieta (2010) that the length of service of an employee significantly influenced the way they manage their work. However, the number of years as principal posted insignificant relationship to the aspect of budgeting since the probability is greater than .05. This means that whether the principal is a novice or experienced in the position, his or her budgeting practice will just be the same or comparable.

d) In-Service Training Attended

The principals' in-service training attended related to management or leadership has high significant relationship on their managerial practices in terms of planning, organizing, supervising and staffing, significant in leading, while insignificant in controlling and budgeting. This indicates that the more seminars and in-service training are attended by the principal, the more that he or she will improve his or her way of setting of objectives and determining a course of action for achieving school's objectives, the more he/she becomes more systematic in the process of structuring, integrating, coordinating task and activities to resources in order to attain

objectives, the more he/she becomes effective in monitoring and regulating subordinates on their responsibilities to improve instruction, and in managing and keeping manned the positions provided for the organizational structure and in appraising and selecting candidates for the positions, compensating or training candidates and incumbents to accomplish their tasks effectively.

I. *Problems Encountered by the Teachers in Terms of their Principals' Managerial Practices*

Every manager in school organization performs certain roles/tasks for the smooth running and improvement of the school but like other organizations managerial problems cannot be avoided. Ukeje (1999) stated that leadership means influencing people to work willingly with zeal towards the achievement of the corporate goals. A manager cannot work alone; he must have people to influence, direct, carry along, sensitize and mobilize towards the achievement of the corporate goal. Some managers are more interested in the performance being done than in the people they work with while others pay more attention to their relationship and satisfaction of their employee. Whether a manager emphasizes the task or people, human relation is usually considered as the central to their managerial practices. Based from the results of the survey questionnaire on problems encountered by the teachers to the managerial practices of their principals, it shows that almost all of them answered that they seldom have problem as manifested by their claim that their principals are effective and that they are very satisfied to their job as teachers.

Based from the follow-up interview of the researcher with some teacher-respondents, the most common problem encountered on the managerial practices of the principals in terms of planning was that the principal does not give orientations to the teachers on how to prepare and implement action plans. In terms of controlling, evaluation is not conducted immediately after the implementation of the target plans. Joves (2013) stated in her study that many managers choose to rely on intuition. They depend upon bright ideas, their personal ability or that of their subordinates for the successful accomplishment of their jobs. She also emphasized that to be an effective school manager, one must be competent in the performance of the various tasks, functions and activities. In the aspect of leading, lack of interest in sending teachers in seminars/conferences is the most pressing problem. This shows that most of the principals do not send their teachers to seminars or in-service training to enhance their professional growth. The last problem is on the supervisory practice of principals. Teachers claimed that principals seldom or do not supervise them at all in their teaching/learning assignments. Having a minimal problem encountered by the teachers on the managerial practices of the principals means that they are satisfied in the way their principals manage the school and most of the managerial practices expected to them are being applied and provided. Forbes (2011) stated in his article that effective school managers are expected to be academically goal oriented and supervise instructional and co-curricular practices accordingly. They motivate and support the

teachers, encourage the community and other school stakeholders to be involved in the educational program, and encourage participatory decision making. They are also faced with the complex task of creating a school wide vision, being an instructional leader- planning for effective professional development, guiding teachers, handling discipline, attending important events and needs, and all the other minute details that come with supervising and managing a school. The job of a school principal is not more demanding and difficult than an ordinary teacher, is expected to be equal, hence “the quality of school principals as school managers is a factor in improving the quality of education”.

According to the study of Salfi (2011), majority of the head teachers of successful schools developed a common and shared school vision and promoted a culture of collaboration, support and trust. They empowered others to lead and distributed leadership responsibilities throughout the school; developed and maintained good relationships among different personnel of school community; and emphasized the professional growth and development of teachers as well as themselves for the process of school improvement.

J. Proposed Managerial Practices Model for Principals in Private Elementary Schools

Based from the results of the correlational analysis of the data, the principals' management practices are positively correlated to their personal profile as well as the job satisfaction and job performance of their teachers. To supplement the results of the correlation analysis, regression analysis was done. This analysis further explains the contributions of all the variables affecting the managerial practices of the principals by computing their multiple coefficient of determinations. Multiple coefficient of determination tells or predicts the percentage of change in the dependent variables as attributed or affected by the change of the independent variables.

Regression analysis revealed that in terms of the personal attributes of the principals, multiple coefficient of determinations were recorded as follows: 74% to planning, 78% to organizing, 81% to controlling, 86% to leading, 79% to supervising, 75% to staffing, and 12% to budgeting practice of principals. These percentages of change in the managerial practices of principals are attributed to the change in their personal attributes. This means that when

taken as a whole, the personal attributes of the principals are predictors of effective managerial practices of principals except in budgeting ($R^2 = 12\%$). Analysis further revealed that when taken singly the age of the principals has the least contribution ($R^2 = 34\%$) in changing the managerial practices of the principals particularly on planning, organizing, supervising, staffing, and budgeting. These analyses show that principal requires maturity to become more effective in leading and controlling, ideal and extensive knowledge which may be gained in enrolling advanced education in all aspects of managerial practices, longer exposure to his or her functions, duties and responsibilities contribute to better planning, organizing, controlling, leading, supervising and staffing, and they need to attend more seminars to enhance and update on the current trends and innovations in education to be effective in planning, organizing, leading, supervising and staffing.

Analysis further revealed that 85% of the change in the level of job satisfaction of teachers is attributed to the change in the level of effectiveness of their principals' managerial practices. Likewise, 89% of the change in the level of job performance of teachers is attributed to the change in the level of effectiveness of their principals' managerial practices. Of the seven managerial practices of the principals, six are predictors of job satisfaction and job performance of teachers and only budgeting registered the least contribution both in the job satisfaction ($R^2 = 0.19$) and job performance ($R^2 = 0.24$) of the teachers. These results show that effectiveness of principals' managerial practices in setting goals, organizing schedules, evaluating performance, inspiring and encouraging subordinates, establishing rapport with teachers and hiring teachers according to needs and qualifications are necessary for their teachers to feel contentment in their job and if teachers are contented or satisfied, they tend to perform better in pursuing their roles and functions as a classroom managers.

Based on these results, a model on the Managerial Practices of Principals in Private Elementary School in the Four Western Towns of Tarlac as shown in Figure 2 is hereby proposed. This model can be used as basis for school administrators in hiring and selecting the best principals with regards to their qualifications and managerial practices that fit and satisfy the needs of the schools in order to effectively implement and realize their vision and mission.

Figure 2. Proposed Managerial Practices Model for Principals in Private Elementary School in the Four Western Towns of Tarlac

VI. SUMMARY, CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This chapter presents the summary of the findings, the conclusions drawn and the recommendations based from the findings and conclusions.

A. SUMMARY

This study was conducted to describe principals' personal attributes and managerial practices, and the job satisfaction and job performance of teachers in private elementary schools. It also determined the extent of difference between the self-ratings of the principals and the ratings of the teachers in terms of principal's managerial practices and the relationship of principal's managerial practices to their personal attributes and to the job satisfaction and job performance of their teachers. It determined the problems encountered by the teachers in terms of principal's managerial practices.

The respondents of the study were fifteen (15) principals and one hundred five (105) teachers in private elementary schools in four western towns of Tarlac during the school year 2018 - 2019.

Data were gathered, tabulated and analysed using descriptive-comparative-correlational research method. Five sets of questionnaire were used; two for the principals and the other sets were for the teacher respondents.

B. FINDINGS

- In terms of the personal attributes of the principals in private schools, most of them (33.33 %) have age ranging from 40-49 years old, most of them (33.33%) are masters' graduate, majority (53.63%) have been a principal for five years or less and majority (66.66%) have attended seminars/in-service trainings related to management and leadership in regional level.
- The principals rated their managerial practices *very effective* (4.54) while their teachers rated them as *effective* (4.27).
- With regards to teacher's job satisfaction, they were *very satisfied* with the security, work environment, job responsibilities and community linkages in their organization.
- In terms of teachers' job performance, the overall weighted mean (4.17) with a verbal description of *very satisfactory* is an indication that they performed well on their instructional competence, professional and personal characteristics and punctuality of attendance.
- As to the self-ratings of the principals compared to the ratings of their teachers on principal's managerial practices, significant difference was noted.
- As to the relationship of principals' managerial practices to the job satisfaction of the teachers, the managerial practices of principals like planning, controlling, leading and staffing have high significant association to the level of job satisfaction of the teachers in terms of security, work environment, job responsibilities and community linkages. Organizing and supervising are significantly related while

budgeting has no significant relation to the job satisfaction of the teachers.

- As to the relationship of principals' managerial practices to the job performance of the teachers, almost all the principals' managerial practices have high significant relationship to the job performance of the teachers in terms of their instructional competence, professional and personal characteristics and punctuality of attendance. However, budgeting as one of the aspects of managerial practices has no significant association to the performance of the teachers.
- The educational attainment, numbers of years as principal and in-service training attended have high significant relationship to the managerial practices of the principals.
- The most pressing problems encountered by the teachers with their principals with regards to their managerial practices on planning, controlling, leading and supervising are: principal does not give orientations to the teachers on how to prepare and implement action plans; lack of interest in sending teachers in seminars/conferences and principals seldom; and others do not supervise them at all in their teaching/learning assignments.
- As to the result of correlations and regression analyses of variables of the study, that managerial practices of principals are predictors and correlates of job satisfaction and job performance of teachers and personal profile of principals are correlates and predictors of their managerial practices, a model of Managerial Practices of Principals in Private Elementary Schools in four Western Towns of Tarlac was proposed.

C. CONCLUSIONS

Based on the findings, the following conclusions were drawn:

- Majority of the principals in private schools are more than 40 years old, with graduate schooling, still new in the position as principal and attending in-service trainings related to management in the regional level.
- The overall managerial practices of the principals are rated *effective* by themselves and their teachers.
- Teachers are very satisfied with their job in terms of security, work environment, job responsibilities and community linkages.
- Performance rating of the teachers based from their academic coordinators/principals is *very satisfactory*.
- Principals have different perceptions on their managerial practices as compared to their teachers.
- The managerial practices of the principals are strongly associated to the job satisfaction of the teachers.
- The managerial practices of the principals are significantly related to their teachers' job performance.
- The personal attributes of the principals are significantly related to their managerial practices except for age.
- The top problems encountered by the teachers with their principals' managerial practices on planning, controlling, leading and supervising include: principal

does not give orientations to the teachers on how to prepare and implement action plans; lack of interest in sending teachers in seminars/conferences; and principals seldom while others do not supervise them at all in their teaching/learning assignments.

- The proposed Principals' Managerial Practices Model for Private Elementary Schools depict the association and influence of managerial practices of principals to their personal attributes and to the job satisfaction and job performance of the teachers.

D. RECOMMENDATIONS

On the bases of the findings and conclusions of the study, the following are recommended:

- Since the principals' educational attainment and in-service training attended are related to the level of effectiveness of their managerial practices, school principals should continue enhancing their competencies by enrolling graduate studies and attending relevant trainings/seminars related to leadership and management.
- Similar studies may be conducted making use of other variables to be correlated to principal's managerial practices like school factor, teacher factor, and learner factor.
- Results of the study may be provided to the principals of private elementary schools in four western towns of Tarlac for their analysis and reflection.
- The proposed Managerial Practices Model for Principals may be adopted as reference towards attaining effective managerial practices of principals in private schools in the four western towns of Tarlac.

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